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The spring potato crop also responded positively to the application of green manure; on average, 17% in 1995 and 81% in 1996 (see table). Vegetative production of the pea, lupin, and faba bean crops was much greater in 1996 than in 1995, possibly because of a combination of seasonal effects and improved management during the second year (inoculation

of the lupin crop and more timely irrigations). Although significant responses to green manure incorporation were measured in both the rice and potato crops, analysis of soil samples taken before the rice crop was planted showed no significant change in any of the soil parameters measured.

Linear relationship between increase in rice biomass and soil-incorporated legume material from different species over a 2-yr period (1994-96).

Performance of indica/japonica derivatives in wet and boro season in West Bengal, India

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Yield and profitability of rice grown in boro season (November-May) in eastern India and Bangladesh could be increased if indica varieties with cold tolerance during the seedling and early vegetative stages are available. Furthermore, farmers prefer varieties that can be grown successfully in both the boro and wet season (June-October). IR36 is now widely used by farmers in West Bengal, India, but its performance is not satisfactory. Some hybrids have shown good performance in the boro season, but their high seed cost is a setback.

Three tolerant indica-type advanced lines developed from indica/japonica or indica/tropical japonica crosses (I/J) with putatively moderate cold tolerance at the seedling stage—(1) IR57098-2B-10-2 (IR31868-64-2-3-3-3/Leng Kwang), (2) IR58565-12-2-2 (Bg94/SR4095-19-2-3-5-4), and (3) IR61608-3B-20-2-2-1 (IR32429-47-3-2-2/Dobong byeo/Moroberakan) were tested for yield along with IR36 and hybrid CNHR3. Entries were grown in Anandapur and Midnapore, West Bengal, in the 1996-97 boro season and 1997 wet season to determine whether I/J derivatives were better than IR36 and CNHR3 for cultivation in both seasons. In the wet season,

entries were tested under both irrigated transplanted conditions and rainfed direct-seeded conditions with 60-13.2-24.9 kg NPK ha⁻¹. Trials were conducted in a randomized complete block design with four replications. The net plot size harvested for yield estimation was 10 m² for the seeded trial. In the boro season, fertilizer level was 100-22-41.5 kg NPK ha⁻¹ with a harvested net plot size of 11.25 m². The experimental design was the same as in the

wet season. All experimental fields were hand-weeded. Insecticides were not applied because there was no visible pest damage.

The table summarizes data on days to flowering and yield obtained from the experiments. The direct-seeded rainfed experiment was affected by drought during the vegetative stage. As a result, flowering was delayed and yields were low—about one-third less than those of the irrigated

Days to flowering and mean grain yield of three indica/japonica derivatives, indica hybrid CNHR3, and IR36 tested in wet and boro seasons in Anandapur, West Bengal, India.

Genotype	Wet season				Boro season		Mean (t ha ⁻¹)
	Direct-seeded and rainfed		Transplanted and irrigated		Transplanted		
	Days to flowering	Yield ^a (t ha ⁻¹)	Days to flowering	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Days to flowering	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	
IR57098-2B-10-2	80	3.2 b	78	4.0 d	125	6.2 c	4.5
IR58565-12-2-2	84	3.8 a	77	5.9 a	124	9.2 a	6.3
IR61608-3B-20-2-2-1	82	3.2 b	77	5.2 b	126	8.0 ab	5.5
CNHR3	74	2.6 c	78	4.7 c	123	9.2 a	5.5
IR36	77	2.1 d	80	4.0 d	130	7.0 bc	4.4
Mean	79	3.0	78	4.7	126	7.0	
CV(%)		7.7		7.3		12.8	

^aMeans followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test.

*Deceased

transplanted experiment. The three I/J derivatives were significantly better than IR36 and the hybrid. The difference in days to flowering between the wet season and boro season was 47 on average. In the boro season, one I/J derivative (IR58565-12-2-2) and the hybrid produced comparable yields and outyielded IR36. Mean yield over three experiments was also highest in IR58565-12-2-2.

Low temperature during plant growth prolonged growth duration in the boro season. Previous observations suggested that in plants putatively tolerant of low temperature, crop duration was less extended in the boro season than in the wet season. In this study, although the I/J derivatives were believed to possess some cold tolerance, their crop duration in the boro season did not differ from cold-sen-

sitive CNHR3 and IR36. With more stable performance over seasons and planting methods and low seed cost, the I/J derivative IR58565-12-2-2 had a significant advantage. Further research is needed to establish a stronger basis for selection of cold tolerance in rice.

Effective land preparation for wet seeding on a reclaimed saline soil in Korea

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We examined the appropriate land preparation method for wet seeding on the wet surface of a reclaimed saline soil in Korea. The experimental field contained 0.2-0.4% NaCl in soil solution. The experiment was conducted at the Gyehwa substation of the NHAES during 1996-97. The experiment involved three tillage treatments (no tillage, 3-5 cm rototilling, and plowing followed by rototilling) in a randomized complete block design with three replicates.

Heading date, culm length, panicle length, and panicle number were similar in the no-tillage and tillage treatments. In rototilled and plow + rototilled treatments, vertical and horizontal root distribution was more uniform than in no tillage (see figure). But about half of the crops in the no-tillage plot lodged at maturity, probably because of their more shallow root distribution.

Spikelet number per unit area and percentage of ripened grains increased significantly, particularly in the plowing treatment followed by rototilling. Milled rice yield increased significantly with tillage but 1000-grain weight was not affected.

Results indicated that the best land preparation for wet seeding on puddled, reclaimed saline soil was to plow in autumn and rototill in spring before seeding (see table).

Percent root distribution as affected by land preparation for wet seeding on reclaimed saline soil, Gyehwa, Korea, 1996-97.

Some agronomic characteristics, yield components, and yield of wet-seeded rice as affected by land preparation method on the wet surface of a reclaimed saline soil, Gyehwa, Korea, 1996-97.

Treatment	Heading date	Culm length (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Panicles m ² (no. x 1000)	Lodging	Spikelets (no.)	Ripened grain (%)	1000-grain weight (g)	Milled rice yield (t ha ⁻¹)
No tillage (control)	11 Aug	62	20	10	5	29.4 c	86.6 b	23.6 a	5.1 c
Rototilled (3-5 cm)	13 Aug	66	20	11	3	32.2 b	92.3 a	23.4 a	5.2 b
Plow tillage + rototilling	13 Aug	68	20	11	0	35.3 a	92.1 a	23.5 a	5.5 a

*Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test.